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Hematopoietic derived factors associated with aging expressed in aged HSC.

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Gpr6, Gpr27, Gpr20, Gpr135, Gpr153 and Gpr15 marked the young human HSC. Instead, Gpr180, Gpr146, Gpr180, Gpr137b and Gpr173 identified the aged HSC.